

CYCLIC DIRECTED PROBABILISTIC GRAPHICAL MODEL: A PROPOSAL BASED ON STRUCTURED OUTCOMES

Probabilistic graphical models are extensively used in the field of data analysis, machine learning, and artificial intelligence [1]. In fact, such models are a set of random variables (graph nodes), whose values reflect (modeling) some important properties in the world, for example in case we model a coin toss experiment our variables will reflect a coins and values will reflect the side of the coin i.e., head or tail. Variables are connected by a probabilistic relationship (graph edges), also known as joint probability distributions (PD), and edges reflect the relationships of the properties of the world [2]. The edges of the graph can be undirected and directed. Additionally, the directionality of the edges allows the model to capture the type of world property relationships, such as causality.

Presently, two types of probabilistic graph models—Bayesian and Markov networks— as well as their variations, are widely used in practice [1, 2, 3]. Bayesian network is a directed acyclic graph (DAG) and can model directed relationships but cannot directly model cyclic relationships. A Markov network (also known as Markov Random Fields) is a undirected cyclic graph (UCG); hence, it can model cyclic relationships, but only if they are in canonical form, while it cannot model directed relationships [4].

However, as practice shows, in many cases, relationships between the properties of the world can be directed and cyclic [5]; hence, a directed cyclic graph (DCG) is required to capture them. This is especially evident in the process of building a network structure from a dataset (structural learning). In general, Markov and Bayesian networks can model such relationships; however, this will make the model complex. For example, in Markov networks, additional variables encoding the type of relationship can be used for this purpose. Alternatively, in Bayesian networks, this can be achieved by representing DCG in the form of several DAGs [6].

Other researchers have also noticed the difficulties associated with modeling cyclic directional relationships and have offered their own solutions. For example, in a previous study [7], Kłopotek M. proposed to interpret the Bayesian network in terms of the Markov process, thereby allowing the existence of cyclic dependencies in Bayesian network graph. The problem with this approach is that the Bayesian network is represented as a Markov chain, which can potentially be infinite. In another study [5], authors proposed to extend existing learning algorithms and causal inference algorithms in DAG models (such as Bayesian networks) by adding necessary support for the cyclic dependencies between random variables. In contrast, our work focuses more on developing a new model rather than making improvement to algorithms of known models. Certain papers [8, 9] show the application of Markov networks for modeling directed cyclic

dependencies. However, since a Markov network is, by definition, a UCG, this requires additional complication of its graphical structure.

The main objective of this work is to define a graphical probabilistic model capable of directly capturing the complex relationships between the properties of the world; predominantly, directions and cyclic relationships. However, in the course of the work, we found a way to classify relationships into a general type that includes (but is not limited to) directionality. We have named this model the probabilistic relation network (PRN) to emphasize the central meaning of relationships contained in it.

Such a model, on one hand, can be built from large datasets without excessive complexity. On the other hand, it will be capable of reflecting the relations of the properties of the world more accurately, which will increase the accuracy and adequacy of the probabilistic inferences in practical applications.

At the core of the PRN lays the following trivial idea: The outcome of some experiments can be represented not just by a point in sample space [10] but also by a graph reflecting the outcome's structure. In the graph, we can represent the outcome as a set of probabilistic events, which will be vertices, and represent the relations between these events as edges. Additionally, each vertex (event) will belong to a random variable, which together forms a relation network.

For example, let us imagine an experiment in which we simultaneously toss a pair of coins, say 25¢ and 50¢. Suppose we are interested not only in how the coins fall out but also in what order they touch the ground. As such, each coin toss result can be represented by a graph of a pair of vertices, each of which is the value “*head*” or “*tail*,” belonging to the random variable “25¢” or “50¢.” Additionally, the directed edge between the values is the order the coins touched the ground. Notably, this experiment can also be easily modeled using a Markov network, but this would require an additional variable with the values “25¢ then 50¢” and “50¢ then 25¢.”

The result of some experiment or trial will be called an **outcome** [11]. In our case, each outcome is a connected graph of arbitrary values/events and the relations between them.

Definition: *An outcome is a connected graph $\omega = \langle \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{r} \rangle$. The vertices of which are arbitrary events $e \in \mathbf{e}$, belonging to some measurable space $(\mathbf{E}, \mathcal{G})$ and $e(\omega) \in \mathcal{G}$, where $e(\omega)$ is the set of e included in ω , and the edges are typed relations $(e_1 \cap^r e_2) \ni \mathbf{r}$ of some arbitrary r from the set of possible types of relations \mathbf{R} .*

Notably, this definition does not impose any restrictions on the type of values e (vertices) and relations r (edges).

Each outcome can have a certain probability ranging from 0 to 1. In this study, we use the frequency interpretation of probability (frequentist probability approach) [12], but other interpretations are also possible.

Definition: *The probability of an outcome is defined as*

$$P(\omega) = \lim_{|T| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\omega(T)|}{|T|}, (1)$$

where $|T|$ denotes the total number of experiments performed and $|\omega(T)|$ denotes the number of experiments with a specific outcome ω . Moreover, $\omega(T) \subseteq T$.

We can now define a **probability space** [10] as the set of all possible outcomes (i.e., all possible connected graphs).

Definition: A probability space is a triple (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) , where Ω denotes the set of connected graphs ω that can be formed on the vertex set \mathbf{E} using the edges set \mathbf{R} , the event set \mathcal{F} is the same as the vertex set \mathbf{E} , and the event probability function $P: \mathbf{E} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0,1]$ is

$$P(e) = \sum_{\{\omega \in \Omega | e(\omega) \ni e\}} P(\omega), (2)$$

where $\{\omega \in \Omega | e(\omega) \ni e\}$ is the set of outcomes ω that include an event e .

We can count the possible number of outcomes in Ω using the formula

$$|\Omega| = \left((|\mathbf{R}| + 1)^{\frac{|\mathbf{E}| * (|\mathbf{E}| - 1)}{2}} \right) + |\mathbf{E}|, (3)$$

where $|\mathbf{R}|$ denotes the number of relations and $|\mathbf{E}|$ denotes the number of events.

As in other probabilistic graphical models [2], the vertices of a PRN are **random variables**.

Probably, as in other models, a PRN includes random variables of any type (discrete, continuous, and mixed). However, this statement requires further research. In this study, we considered only discrete random variables.

Definition: A random variable V is a measurable function $V: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbf{E}$, where Ω denotes a probability space and \mathbf{E} denotes some measurable space, such that

$$\mathbf{E} \neq \emptyset (4)$$

$$\forall e_1 \in \mathbf{E}, e_2 \in \mathbf{E}, \omega \in \Omega \nexists e(\omega) \ni e_1 \cap e_2; e_1 \neq e_2 (5)$$

$$\forall e_1 \in \mathbf{E}_1, e_2 \in \mathbf{E}_2 \nexists e_1 = e_2. (6)$$

In other words, a random variable V has a domain \mathbf{E} comprising the set of vertices $e \in \mathbf{E}$. Moreover, the probability space Ω should not contain graph ω that includes vertices e that belong to the domain \mathbf{E} of the same V . Additionally, the vertex e can belong to one and only one domain \mathbf{E} (i.e., it can belong to only one variable V).

Notably, in the probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) , we can define arbitrarily many random variables V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n , and each of them can have its arbitrary domain $\mathbf{E}_1, \mathbf{E}_2, \dots, \mathbf{E}_n$.

In the model under study, we allow the existence of outcome ω that does not include any value of some variable V . In other words, we allow an experiment whose result ω does not provide any relevant information about the variable V . To reflect this case in the model and make the model consistent, we assume that each variable contains an **unobservable value**.

Definition: An unobserved value u is a value that is necessarily included in the domain \mathbf{E} of the variable V but not included as a vertex in any outcome $\omega \in \Omega$.

Notably, the value u can be any value from \mathbf{E} . It can be either chosen from those already defined or added specially.

The PD of the values of a variable V is the set of probabilities of the values/events e included in its domain \mathbf{E} , except for the value u , the probability of which can be interpreted as “the probability of nonobservation of the variable V .”

Definition: We extend the probability function $P: \mathbf{E} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}[0,1]$ for a random variable V as

$$P(e) = \begin{cases} \sum_{\{\omega \in \Omega | e(\omega) \ni e\}} P(\omega); & e \neq u \\ 1 - \sum_{\{e \in \mathbf{E} | e \neq u\}} P(e); & e = u \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where $\{\omega \in \Omega | e(\omega) \ni e\}$ is the set of outcomes ω that includes event e and $\{e \in \mathbf{E} | e \neq u\}$ is the set of values of variable V excluding the value u .

Accordingly, the PD of a variable is

$$P(V) = \{P(e) \mid e \in \mathbf{E}\}. \quad (8)$$

Additionally, the sum of the probabilities of all values will always be equal to 1 (see Theorem A):

$$\sum_{e \in \mathbf{E}} P(e) = 1. \quad (9)$$

In practice, we are interested in the PD of V without considering the unobserved value u . We can obtain it via a simple normalization:

$$\dot{P}(V) = \left\{ \frac{P(e)}{\sum_{e \in \mathbf{E}} P(e)} \mid e \in \mathbf{E}, e \neq u \right\}. \quad (10)$$

Now, we have the necessary components to define a PRN.

Definition: A PRN θ is a graph $\langle \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{O} \rangle$, where the set of vertices \mathbf{V} is the set of random variables $V: \mathbf{E}$ on the probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) , \mathbf{R} is the set of relation types between values of V , and $\mathbf{O} = \{\omega \in \Omega \mid P(\omega) \neq 0\}$. Moreover, a pair of vertices $V_1, V_2 \in \mathbf{V}$ are connected by an edge if and only if there exists $\omega \in \mathbf{O}$ containing the relation $e_1 \cap^r e_2$, where $e_1 \in \mathbf{E}_1$ and $e \in \mathbf{E}_2$.

In essence, we can think of a PRN as simply a set of outcomes ω with nonzero probability, whose vertex values e are combined into variables $V: \mathbf{E}$. The edges of the network simply show some probabilistic dependence between vertices V_1 and V_2 .

Notably, this definition does not impose any restrictions on the types of edges (including directed or not) or on the graph's structure. It also admits the existence of θ with no outcomes in it (i.e., $\mathbf{O} = \emptyset$); in this case, the PD of each variable V will be concentrated in the unobserved value u [i.e., $P(u) = 1$ and $\forall e \in \mathbf{E}: P(e) = 0$]. Additionally, a pair of vertices $\dot{V}_1: \dot{\mathbf{E}}_1, \dot{V}_2: \dot{\mathbf{E}}_2 \in \mathbf{V}$ of θ are independent (i.e., $\dot{V}_1 \perp \dot{V}_2$) if there is no outcome ω such that $\dot{\mathbf{E}}_1, \dot{\mathbf{E}}_2 \subseteq e(\omega)$. In other words, $\dot{V}_1 \perp \dot{V}_2$ if there is no path between them. Meanwhile, nonnormalized V_1 and V_2 are dependent, via the unobserved value u .

Assuming that each variable V has the same number of values (i.e., $\forall V_1: \mathbf{E}_1, V_2: \mathbf{E}_2 \in \mathbf{V} \nexists: |\mathbf{E}_1| \neq |\mathbf{E}_2|$), we can calculate the maximum number of outcomes as follows:

$$|\mathbf{O}| = \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathbf{V}|} \left(\binom{|\mathbf{V}|}{k} * C_k * (|\mathbf{E}| - 1)^k \right), \quad (11)$$

where

$$C_k = (|\mathbf{R}| + 1)^{\frac{k*(k-1)}{2}} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \left(i * \binom{k}{i} * (|\mathbf{R}| + 1)^{\frac{(k-i)*(k-i-1)}{2}} * C_i \right)}{k}, \quad (12)$$

$|\mathbf{R}|$ denotes the number of relation types, $|\mathbf{V}|$ denotes the number of vertices in \mathbf{O} , and $|\mathbf{E}|$ denotes the number of values at each vertex including the unobserved u .

In many cases, we will work with the probabilities of specific outcomes, so we introduce the concept of **outcome PD**.

Definition: We define an outcome PD as follows:

$$P(\mathbf{O}) = \{P(\omega) \mid \omega \in \mathbf{O}\}. \quad (13)$$

A **full joint PD** is the set of probabilities of all combinations of values of all variables, in the context of a PRN \mathbf{O} , i.e., a set of outcomes, each of which includes one value from each variable V constituting \mathbf{O} .

Definition: A PRN containing a full joint PD is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{O}} = \langle \hat{\mathbf{V}}, \hat{\mathbf{R}}, \{\omega \in \hat{\mathbf{O}} \mid V(\omega) = \hat{\mathbf{V}}\} \rangle, \quad (14)$$

where $V(\omega)$ denotes the set of variables whose values are included in the outcome ω .

In this case, the full joint PD is

$$P(\hat{\mathbf{V}}) = \{P(\hat{V}) \mid \hat{V} \in \hat{\mathbf{V}}\}. \quad (15)$$

Notably, $\hat{\mathbf{O}}$ need not contain outcomes for all possible combinations of values but only outcomes with nonzero probability.

A **conditional PD** can be represented as a subset of outcomes from \mathbf{O} that is consistent with some observed outcome.

Definition: A PRN containing a conditional PD is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{O}|\tilde{\omega} &= \langle \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{R}, \{\omega \in \mathbf{O} \mid (V(\tilde{\omega}) \cap V(\omega)) \\ &= \emptyset \bigvee (e(\tilde{\omega}) \subseteq e(\omega) \bigwedge r(\tilde{\omega}) \subseteq r(\omega)) \} \rangle, \quad (16) \end{aligned}$$

where $r(\omega)$ denotes the set of relations included in the outcome (edges) and $e(\omega)$ denotes the set of values included in the outcome (outcome vertices).

From a computational perspective, when converting \mathbf{O} to $\mathbf{O}|\tilde{\omega}$, PDs should be normalized as follows:

$$P(\mathbf{O}|\tilde{\omega}) = \left\{ \frac{P(\omega)}{Z} \mid \omega \in \mathbf{O}|\tilde{\omega} \right\}, \quad (17)$$

where Z denotes the normalization constant.

We can convert $\mathbf{O}|\tilde{\omega}$ to a network with full joint PD $\hat{\mathbf{O}}|\tilde{\omega}$ and then obtain conditional PDs of all variables

$$P(\hat{\mathbf{V}}|\tilde{\omega}) = \{P(\hat{V}|\tilde{\omega}) \mid \hat{V} \in \hat{\mathbf{V}}\}. \quad (18)$$

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